

Table S2. Pharmacokinetic parameters after oral administration of lapachol (10 mg/kg and 25 mg/kg) and LAP sodium salt (30 mg/kg) in Wistar rats

Pharmacokinetic Parameter	10 mg/kg oral LAP		25 mg/kg oral LAP		30 mg/kg oral LAP sodium salt	
	NCA	1-Comp	NCA	1-Comp	NCA	1- Comp
C_{max} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	31.6 $\pm$ 3.8	-	65.6 $\pm$ 10.6	-	55.9 $\pm$ 25.8	-
t_{max} (h)	1.2 $\pm$ 0.3	-	1.3 $\pm$ 0.4	-	1.6 $\pm$ 1.1	-
Ka (h^{-1})	-	2.61 $\pm$ 0.85	-	2.93 $\pm$ 0.79	-	1.04 $\pm$ 1.02
Ke (h^{-1})	-	0.17 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.16 $\pm$ 0.02	-	0.25 $\pm$ 0.15
l (h^{-1})	0.16 $\pm$ 0.01	-	0.19 $\pm$ 0.03	-	0.19 $\pm$ 0.07	-
$t_{1/2}$ (h)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.2	-	3.6 $\pm$ 0.5	-	4.3 $\pm$ 2.0	-
$t_{1/2\beta}$ (h)	-	4.2 $\pm$ 0.3	-	4.4 $\pm$ 0.6	-	3.6 $\pm$ 2.0
$AUC_{0-\infty}$ ($\mu\text{g h/ml}$)	216.9 $\pm$ 22.0	237.4 $\pm$ 20.2	449 $\pm$ 78.1	434.3 $\pm$ 79.7	315.2 $\pm$ 140	314 $\pm$ 143.8
CL_{tot} (L/kg)	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01	0.03 $\pm$ 0.03	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01	0.04 $\pm$ 0.01	0.04 $\pm$ 0.02	0.05 $\pm$ 0.03
Vd_{ss} (L/kg)	-	0.19 $\pm$ 0.02	-	0.24 $\pm$ 0.04	-	0.20 $\pm$ 0.09
MRT (h)	7.2 $\pm$ 0.6	-	7.2 $\pm$ 0.7	-	6.5 $\pm$ 2.8	-
F_{abs} (%)	77	-	65	-	42	-

LAP (n = 8, 10 mg/kg); LAP (n = 6, 25 mg/kg); LAP sodium salt (n = 8, 30 mg/kg)